

English

Information and Consent

Welcome

This study is part of a project that explores the **working conditions, professional image and job satisfaction of audio describers**.

To fill in this questionnaire you will need approximately **15-20 minutes**.

The project is managed by Alicja Zajdel (alicja.zajdel@uantwerpen.be) and Anna Jankowska (anna.jankowska@uantwerpen.be) from the University of Antwerp.

Take a note of these emails in case you need them later on.

If you have any doubts before or during the experiment, please contact us.

We are looking for participants who are **professional audio describers**, working in **any type of AD** (film, TV, opera, museum etc.) and in **any**

language.

The questionnaire is available in English, Spanish, Polish, French, Italian and Dutch. You can select the language of your choice from the dropdown menu above.

Information and Consent Form

On the next screen you will find information for participants, followed by the consent form. Please read both screens carefully.

If you have any questions regarding the information provided, this form or the study in general, please contact the researchers via email.

Information for Participants

You are invited to participate in a research study which examines the **working conditions, professional image and job satisfaction of AD practitioners**. You can participate by completing this online questionnaire. The questionnaire will take about **15-20 minutes** to complete.

We will not collect any personal data. This means that the data cannot be traced back to you. The research data we collect during this study will be

used by the researchers as part of data sets, articles, and presentations. To make optimal use of all the collected research data, the data sets may be reused for other research purposes at a later stage.

Your participation in this study is strictly **voluntary** and you have the right to refuse participation. At any time, you have the possibility to either participate in the study or to discontinue your participation, even after having expressed your consent. You do not have to motivate discontinuing your participation. The decision to discontinue your participation will not cause you any harm or loss of benefits.

The appointing authority of this study is the **University of Antwerp**. This study has been reviewed by the **Ethics Committee** for the Social Sciences and Humanities at the University of Antwerp, which has formulated a positive advice on 17.02.2022.

If you have questions with regard to the study or your rights as a participant, you can contact Alicja Zajdel (alicja.zajdel@uantwerpen.be) or Anna Jankowska (anna.jankowska@uantwerpen.be).

Thank you for reading through this information screen and for considering taking part in this study.

Consent Form

If you **check each box**, you are **consenting** to take part in the study.

If you **DO NOT** check **ALL** boxes, it will mean that you **DO NOT** agree to take part in the experiment and you will **exit** this survey.

If you have questions before consenting, please contact Alicja Zajdel (alicja.zajdel@uantwerpen.be) or Anna Jankowska (anna.jankowska@uantwerpen.be).

I confirm that I have read and understood the information about this study. I was given sufficient time to consider the information and to ask questions, to which I have received adequate answers.

I have fully understood that I can discontinue my participation in this study at any time without this having any disadvantages.

I am aware of the goal for which the data provided by me will be collected, processed and used within the framework of this study and that they will be treated in a confidential manner.

I agree to the collection, processing and use of these data, as described in the information sheet for the participant.

I agree to the reuse of the research data provided by me for other research purposes.

I voluntarily agree to participate in this study.

I am willing to provide information regarding my participation in possible follow-up studies.

For this study we are working with QUALTRICS. Please be informed about the privacy policy and potential recent updates before you agree to participate in our study. You can find this information [here](#).

Do you agree with the QUALTRICS privacy statement?

Yes, I am over 18 years old, have read the Qualtrics privacy statement and agree with their policies.

No, I have not read the Qualtrics privacy statement and/or do not agree with their policies.

Background Information

What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- Primary
- Secondary
- Vocational education
- BA/BSc
- MA/MSc
- PhD

What is your educational background? [multiple answers possible]

- Language and linguistics
- Literature
- Translation
- Film and TV studies
- Theatre studies
- Acting school
- Arts and/or museum studies
- Psychology
- Journalism or media studies
- Science
- Computer science and IT
- Other, please specify:

How long have you been working as an audio describer (in any area of

AD, e.g., film, TV, live events)?

Less than 1 year

1-5 years

6-10 years

11-15 years

Over 15 years

Which of the following AD types have you worked with the most in the last 5 years? [multiple answers possible]

Film

TV

Museum

Theatre

Opera

Other live events

Other, please specify:

Which of the following stages of the production process do you have experience with (in any area of AD, e.g., film, TV, live events)? [multiple answers possible]

Writing and/or revising the AD script

Translating AD scripts

Using machine translation with post-editing

Voicing AD

Assisting at recording AD with voice talents

Mixing the AD with the original soundtrack

Quality control of the final product (e.g. checking the script or recording or both)

Other, please specify:

What job title(s) do you use for yourself?

Where do you live?

In which language(s) do you write AD?

Do you work for national or international clients? (Note: national clients are based in the country where you live)

National

International

Both

Which of the following best describes your current employment status?

Freelancer

Employed

Working conditions

Have you received specific AD training?

Yes

No

In what form? [multiple answers possible]

Workshop

Vocational course

University course

Internship

In-house training

One-to-one instruction

Online course

Other, please specify:

Do you take part in any professional development activities? (e.g., courses, workshops etc.)

Yes

No

Does your employer provide you with opportunities to continue your professional development? (e.g., courses, workshops etc.)

Yes

No

What are they?

What percentage of your income comes from AD assignments?

Less than 25%

25-50%

51-75%

More than 75%

I don't know

What percentage of your work time do you dedicate to AD assignments?

Less than 25%

25-50%

51-75%

More than 75%

I don't know

Are you satisfied with your income level?

Very satisfied

Fairly satisfied

Neither satisfied not dissatisfied

Fairly dissatisfied

Very dissatisfied

To what extent can you influence the following:

	To a very low degree or not at all	To a low degree	To a certain degree	To a high degree	To a very high degree
Your working hours	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The clients you work for	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The AD tasks you accept	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	To a very low degree or not at all	To a low degree	To a certain degree	To a high degree	To a very high degree
Your fees or your income level	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The quality of the completed AD tasks	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

How often do you have to compromise the quality of your work due to external factors (such as deadlines)?

- Always
- Most of the time
- Sometimes
- Occasionally
- Never

How often have you experienced negative, work-related stress in the past year?

- Daily
- Weekly
- Monthly
- Occasionally
- Never

What are the main causes of stress? [multiple answers possible]

- Tight deadlines
- Unfair payment
- Interactions with clients
- Interactions with colleagues
- Interactions with the employer
- Lack of feedback
- Unsuitable workspace
- Unsuitable work equipment
- Other, please specify:

Have you considered leaving the profession over the past year?

- Daily
- Weekly
- Monthly
- Occasionally
- Never

How often do you discuss AD problems with...

	Never	Occasionally	Monthly	Weekly	Daily
Other audio describers?	<input type="radio"/>				

	Never	Occasionally	Monthly	Weekly	Daily
Blind and partially sighted patrons?	<input type="radio"/>				
Clients?	<input type="radio"/>				
Your employer?	<input type="radio"/>				

How often do you receive feedback on the quality of your work?

Always

Most of the time

Sometimes

Occasionally

Never

Do your clients or your employer trust the quality of your work?

To a very high degree

To a high degree

To a certain degree

To a low degree

To a very low degree or not at all

I don't know

Do your clients or your employer consider your work important?

To a very high degree

To a high degree

To a certain degree

To a low degree

To a very low degree or not at all

I don't know

Where do you usually work?

In an office in my home

In some other room in my home

In an office outside my home

Other, please specify:

Do you share your office?

No, I work alone

Yes, with 1 person

Yes, with 2-4 people

Yes, with 5-9 people

Yes, with 10 people or more

Do you have a dedicated workspace (i.e., a desk/table not shared with

anyone else or used for any other function)?

Yes

No

Which software do you use to complete your AD assignments? [multiple answers possible]

AD software

Subtitling software

CAT tools

Text editor

Voice recording software

Video-editing software

Other, please specify:

Do you have enough time for yourself or your family outside of work?

Always

Most of the time

Sometimes

Occasionally

Never

Professional Image

To what extent do you think...

	To a very low degree or not at all	To a low degree	To a certain degree	To a high degree	To a very high degree
AD involves creativity?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
AD requires expert skills?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
AD is a prestigious job?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
audio describers are visible as a professional group in society?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
the work of an audio describer has an economic, political or social impact?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
audio describers are valued in society?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Job Satisfaction

In my present job, this is how I feel about...

	Not satisfied	Somewhat satisfied	Satisfied	Very satisfied	Extremely satisfied
The chance to work alone on the job	<input type="radio"/>				
The chance to do different things from time to time	<input type="radio"/>				
The chance to be 'somebody' in the community	<input type="radio"/>				
Being able to do things that do not go against my conscience	<input type="radio"/>				
The way my job provides for steady employment	<input type="radio"/>				
The chance to do things for other people	<input type="radio"/>				
The chance to do something that makes use of my abilities	<input type="radio"/>				
My pay and the amount of work I do	<input type="radio"/>				

	Not satisfied	Somewhat satisfied	Satisfied	Very satisfied	Extremely satisfied
The freedom to use my own judgment	<input type="radio"/>				
The chance to try my own methods of doing the job	<input type="radio"/>				
The working conditions	<input type="radio"/>				
The feeling of accomplishment I get from the job	<input type="radio"/>				

Considering all aspects of your job, how satisfied are you overall?

Extremely satisfied

Very satisfied

Satisfied

Somewhat satisfied

Not satisfied

Is there anything you would like to add relating to the topics covered in this questionnaire?

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